

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IKONDERE****FIRST NAME: MARVIN****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author didn't use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

1. Research writing (Euclid 2019, 1)
2. Writing the essay (Euclid 2019, 5)
3. Referencing (Euclid 2019, 9)
4. Style and language of writing (Euclid 2019, 40)

ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In period one, I began the study of the concept of international academic writing. academic writing forms the basis of academic work and therefore must be well written. my study was mainly informed by the course material for the first period. the key elements of academic essay writing form the basis of period one and include; answering a question, have a thesis statement and present or discuss something (Euclid 2019, 1). this response paper will therefore focus on the areas of research, writing the essay, referencing, style and language of writing.

2) RESEARCH

Research forms a key feature of academic writing and is vital for any essay (EUCLID 2019, 2). Academic essay writing draws on the work other writers and Researchers. The value is to read and carry out research in order to have a good essay. Researching helps to provide the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the question. Reading and research should be done at the earliest possible time to familiarize with the topic and develop your ideas. After reading that you make notes with the question in mind for example you must use the evidence especially relevant examples to support the arguments you are putting across (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Essay Writing requires creative and critical thinking. On the one hand, creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas for example through techniques like brain storming or mind mapping while on the other hand critical thinking encourages you to narrow the focus or scope of your ideas for example asking why an example is important to your argument (EUCLID 2019, 4). Thinking helps you predetermine your answer and research that will help with your essay writing. Creative thinking should be encouraged for any essay writing as this helps to broaden the scope of the answer instead of the same monotonous answer to the question. I believe that critical thinking is what separates an ‘A’ student from a ‘B’ student. Critical thinking is usually good however sometimes with narrowed mind your ideas are clipped and you’re unable to expand into better thinking areas.

The essay should be balanced in such a way that you bring together different views from different authors for example if you are writing on the topic of “What is Diplomacy”? You should be able to gather views from different writers that have defined what diplomacy is. This will help make an informed approach while writing your essay (ibid.).

3) WRITING THE ESSAY

Once the research is completed you organize your ideas into an answer. The ideas should be well developed before you write the essay. A plan should be drawn up on how the essay will be written (ibid.). The essay contains an introduction, body and conclusion. The Introduction should be precise and concise. The body contains paragraphs with each building up on the next paragraph. The essay should be balanced for example the points presented should have a range of points from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant topics of the topic. When writing the essay, it is important to have a first draft which will help you organize your answers to the question. A first draft helps improve your writing and it determines how best to improve your essay.

Moreover, the essay should be arranged in form of paragraphs and should include a topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence or examples and analysis (EUCLID 2019, 5). This is important so that you do not leave the paragraph halfway without critically concluding the paragraph. A conclusion is important to help build up on the next paragraph. In my view, this helps build up on the next paragraph. It is important to keep the essay question in mind and not lose focus as you write the essay.

Once the essay is completed its important to have a conclusion. The conclusion should never introduce new ideas its purpose is to round off your essay by summing up (ibid.).

4) REFERENCING

Referencing is important and vital for any academic writing. Referencing guards against plagiarism which is one of the most grievous academic offences. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the

information (EUCLID 2019, 8). This can involve paraphrasing, copying and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author (EUCLID 2019, 9). Plagiarism is very unethical and highly punishable for example as an undergraduate student of law in Uganda the academic offence of plagiarism would usually amount to suspension. This shows that it's taken very seriously in all academic institutions. In order to avoid plagiarism, it is important to properly cite the author of the works you are citing. Citation is important for any academic work that you have to write. Citation can take the form of in-text citation or list of works cited (EUCLID 2019, 16).

In-text citation is the approved mode of citation for EUCLID response papers. In-text Citation refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself. For example, "Before 1984 footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct" (Gerson and Gerson 143). This is how you cite the information using the in-text citation. The above example and more examples are included in the EUCLID coursepack for period one. In-text referencing is used for quotes and paraphrases. On the one hand quotes are the exact words of the author and it is important to use quotation marks to capture what the author said. Quotations should be used in a limited form as too many of them will make the work lose its value (EUCLID 2019, 23).

On the other hand, paraphrasing is using the ideas and information that an author has produced but written in your own words (*ibid.*). The paraphrases must look different from how the author wrote it and it must be your own words. The language used cannot resemble that of the author (EUCLID 2019, 24). Citation should not be used when the source or information put forward is common knowledge and universally known. If the information is repeated, then you can assume it is common knowledge.

5) STYLE AND LANGUAGE OF WRITING

While writing it is right to apply the academic style of writing. This involves using logical connectors in your work so that there is flow in your work (EUCLID 2019, 39). The style of writing may take on the various forms of academic writing like the Chicago style and the Oxford style of writing however EUCLID recommends the Chicago or Turabian style of writing which is the one I am using for this response paper. Nevertheless, when using a style be consistent and have a style guide to help in determining the style you want to use in writing the paper. A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2019, 40).

The style of writing is much more than punctuation, correct grammar and vocabulary. Style may encompass many different aspects like preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, abbreviations among others. However, for purposes of the academic work and response paper I am writing I will follow the Chicago style of writing or commonly referred to as the Turabian Style. Chicago Style of Writing is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations,

1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press) (EUCLID 2019, 66). One of the unique things about this style is the use of the quotation style for example all quotations should be placed in quotation marks or indented as a block quote. This is unique because usually I place the quote in the essay without paying attention to the block marks and indent. This is something that I have found quite interesting from reading the material.

On the one hand Footnote referencing is for the Chicago style and should be used for any academic writing that uses the Chicago style. Footnotes must be placed or at least must begin on the page where they are referred to (EUCLID 2019, 73). On the other hand, Chicago End Notes are usually cited and arranged in the order cited. Notes are commonly single spaced.

Language especially in academic writing is to help differentiate between the American and British English. This helps to make sure you have consistent language as you write

6) **CONCLUSION**

I believe that the material for academic writing (ACA-401D) has greatly helped me understand the importance of essay writing. I found the course pack material provided very relevant and practical especially with understanding key concepts of academic writing. I found the use of in text referencing very helpful and easier to use than having to footnote. I hope to learn better ways of using the in-text citation. The differences between American and British English were complex to understand seeing am accustomed to using the British English in my academic writing. I have however challenged myself to use the American English and learn how best to incorporate it as I embark on my study programme at EUCLID. I have learnt the importance of academic writing and how best to apply the Turabian style in academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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